

TECHNIQUES FOR EVALUATING THE DEFORMATION PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS

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Hozirgi kunda barcha toifadagi binolar va inshootlarning ishonchliligini oshirishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ayniqsa, deformatsiya va siljish maydonlarini tahlil qilishda turli usullardan foydalanish zarur bo'lib bormoqda, ulardan biri – raqamli golografik interferometriya usulidir. Tarqoq aks ettiruvchi ob'yektlarning harakatini o'lchashda qo'llaniladigan raqamli golografik interferometrlar (DHI) ikkita noyob metrologik xususiyatga ega: harakatlarga nisbatan nihoyatda yuqori sezuvchanlik (nanometrning ulushlarigacha) va ob'yekt yuzasining butun sathida bir vaqtda o'lchov o'tkazish imkoniyati.

Kalit so'zlari: raqamli golografik interferometriya, elastiklik moduli, gologramma, mutlaq qiymat

Currently, considerable attention is paid to improving the reliability of all categories of buildings and structures. Especially for the analysis of deformation and displacement field, the use of various methods is urgently required, one of which is digital holographic interferometry. Digital holographic interferometers (DHI) used to measure the movements of diffuse-reflecting objects have two unique metrological properties: ultra-high sensitivity to movements (fractions of a nanometer) and the ability to perform measurements simultaneously over the entire surface of the object.

Keywords: digital holographic interferometry, modulus of elasticity, hologram, absolute value, breadboard beam

В настоящее время уделяется значительное внимание повышению надежности всех категорий зданий и сооружений. Особенно при анализе поля деформаций и перемещений остро требуется использование различных методов, одним из которых является цифровая голографическая интерферометрия. Цифровые голографические интерферометры (ЦГИ), используемые для

измерения перемещений объектов с диффузным отражением, обладают двумя уникальными метрологическими свойствами: сверхвысокой чувствительностью к перемещениям (доли нанометра) и способностью выполнять измерения одновременно по всей поверхности объекта.

Ключевые слова: цифровая голографическая интерферометрия, модуль упругости, голограмма, абсолютное значение

To date, new methods for obtaining interferometric data have been developed in the world - holographic interferometry. At the same time, much attention is paid to the study of transparent and reflective objects, including diffuse ones. In this area, one of the important tasks is to conduct targeted scientific research in the following areas: the development of ways to increase the sensitivity of holographic interferometry, the search for ways to compensate for distortions that occur at the stage of recording holograms, the development of digital methods of holographic interferometry, the development of optimal schemes for recording digital holograms that minimize technical and economic costs; application of digital holographic interferometry for measuring and analyzing fields of ultra-small displacements, deformations of materials and structures.

On the basis of this method, a model beam design was made, the scheme of which is shown in Fig. 1. The beam was made of D-16 grade duralumin, which was attached to the massive steel plate of the optical table using steel corners. - layout beam loading scheme. Technology options based on the use of photographic materials have found a fairly wide application in experimental mechanics, their capabilities and limitations have been studied and described in detail [1,2]

The elastic line of the vertical part of the beam under pure bending loading is described by the well-known formula [3]:

$$Y = \frac{M}{2EJ} X^2 \quad (1)$$

Here X is the current coordinate of the beam surface point relative to the termination, Y is the deflection (normal displacement) of the surface of the vertical part

of the beam at the point with the X coordinate (Fig. 1.), E is the modulus of elasticity of the beam material.

The moment of inertia of the beam section is determined based on the ratio:

$$J = \frac{bh^3}{12} \quad (2)$$

where b is the width of the beam; h is its thickness.

The bending moment is:

$$M = P \cdot L \quad (3)$$

where P is the magnitude of the force (load weight); L is the shoulder of force application.

In order to compare the results of measurements performed using the CGI with the results of calculations for similar loading parameters of the beam, a series of experiments was carried out. At the same time, for the maximum approximation of the experimental conditions to the calculated ones, i.e. ideal, a precision exemplary beam was made. A technique was also developed and used, including statistical processing of measurement information and corrections.

Fig.1. Model beam diagram

The average value of the measured displacements Y according to the formula:

$$Y_{cp} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^8 Y_i}{8} = 3,44 \text{ } \mu\text{m} \quad (4)$$

Fig.2. Model beam deflection measurement results

The absolute value of the limiting relative deviation of the measured values from the average value of the measured displacements is calculated by the formula:

$$\Delta_{\dot{e}ci} = \frac{\Delta Y}{Y_{\dot{n}d}} = 0,0465 / 3,44 = 0,0135 = 1,35 \% \quad (5)$$

Limit total relative error of displacement measurement

$$\Delta_{\max} = \pm(\Delta_{\dot{e}ci} + \Delta_{i\dot{a}d}) = \pm (1,35 + 5,21) = \pm 6,56\%$$

Here $\pm 5,21 \%$ - errors in the calculation of the elastic line of the beam.

Thus, when carrying out real measurements of small displacements of points of a deformed object, a total relative error of 6.56% was achieved. It is shown that the developed technique can be used to measure the elastic constants, first of all, of "homogeneous" materials, such as metals and their alloys. For this, only a part from the material under study in the form of an "L" shaped beam is needed; also, based on a comparison with tabular data, you can find out from which "unknown" material the beam is made.

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